

1 Supporting information

3 Appendix S1

5 Systematic references

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52 **Table S1.1** Taxonomic reconciliation table including the decisions made to include or exclude some
 53 described taxa from our study and the references on which the decisions were based.

Taxonomic reconciliation	Reference
<i>Graphium deliae</i> (Libert & Collins, 2007) was included.	Libert, M. (2007) Note on the Genus <i>Graphium</i> Scopoli. Lambillionea. Libert, M. (2007). Note on the genus <i>Graphium</i> Scopoli. (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae). Lambillionea, 107(1), 19–29. CVII: 1-11
<i>Papilio bacelarae</i> (Bivar de Sousa & Mendez, 2009) was included.	Bivar de sousa, A. & Mendes, L. F. (2009). On a new species of the genus <i>Princeps</i> Hübner, [1807] from Cabinda (Angola) (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae). <i>SHILAP Revista de Lepidopterologia</i> , 37(147), 327-334.
<i>Papilio rumiko</i> , described in 2014, has been added separately from <i>Papilio cresphontes</i> .	Shiraiwa, K., Cong, Q., & Grishin, N. V. (2014). A new <i>Heraclides</i> swallowtail (Lepidoptera, Papilionidae) from North America is recognized by the pattern on its neck. <i>Zookeys</i> , (468), 85.
<i>Parnassius huberi</i> (Paulus, 1999) was considered.	Paulus, V. (1999). A new species of <i>Parnassius</i> discovered in North Tibet, China (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae, Parnassinae). <i>Wallace</i> , 6, 1-7.
<i>Graphium incertus</i> is synonym of <i>Graphium parus</i> .	Racheli, T. & Cotton, A.M. (2009) Guide to the Butterflies of the Palearctic Region. Papilionidae. Part I. Omnes Artes, Milano, 70 pp
<i>Graphium mandarinus</i> is synonym of <i>Graphium glycerion</i> .	Collins, N. M., & Morris, M. G. (1985). <i>Threatened swallowtail butterflies of the world: the IUCN Red Data Book</i> . lucn.
<i>Graphium timur</i> (Ney, 1911) was synonymized with <i>Graphium mullah</i> following Cotton y Racheli, T., 2007.	Cotton, A.M. & Racheli, T., [2007]. A preliminary annotated checklist of the Papilionidae of Laos with notes on taxonomy, phenology, distribution and variation (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). <i>Fragm. Entomol.</i> 38 (2): 279-378
<i>Iphiclides feisthamelli</i> was considered as a separated species from <i>Iphiclides podalirius</i>	Gaunet, A., Dincă, V., Dapporto, L., Montagud, S., Vodă, R., Schär, S., Badiane, A., Font, E. & Vila, R. (2019). Two consecutive <i>Wolbachia</i> -mediated mitochondrial introgressions obscure taxonomy in Palearctic swallowtail butterflies (Lepidoptera, Papilionidae). <i>Zoologica Scripta</i> , 48(4), 507-519.
<i>Luehdorfia longicaudata</i> was considered as a separated species from <i>Luehdorfia taibai</i> .	Lian-Xi, X., Peng-Fei, L., Jia, W., Kai, W., & Ping, Y. (2014). The complete mitochondrial genome of the endangered butterfly <i>Luehdorfia taibai</i> Chou (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae).
<i>Ornithoptera arfakensis</i> was considered as a separated species from <i>O. paradisea</i>	Adam Cotton personal communication/ Matsuka, H. (2001). <i>Natural history of birdwing butterflies</i> . Matsuka Shuppan.
<i>Papilio appalachiensis</i> was considered different from both <i>P. glaucus</i> and <i>P. canadiensis</i>	Kunte, K., Shea, C., Aardema, M. L., Scriber, J. M., Juenger, T. E., Gilbert, L. E., & Kronforst, M. R. (2011). Sex chromosome mosaicism and hybrid speciation among tiger swallowtail butterflies. <i>PLoS genetics</i> , 7(9), e1002274.
<i>Papilio daedalus</i> was considered different from <i>Papilio palinurus</i> , and restricted to Philippines Islands.	Hardy, P. B., & Lawrence, J. M. (2017). <i>Field guide to butterflies of the Philippines</i> (p. 488). Siri Scientific Press. / Condamine, F. L., Toussaint, E. F., Cotton, A. M., Genson, G. S., Sperling, F. A., & Kergoat, G. J. (2013). Fine-scale biogeographical and temporal diversification processes of peacock swallowtails (<i>Papilio</i> subgenus <i>Achillides</i>) in the Indo-Australian Archipelago. <i>Cladistics</i> , 29(1), 88-111.
Papilio dehaani was considered different from <i>Papilio bianor</i> , and restricted to the Japanese island of Hokkaido	East, R. F., Dubatolov, V. V., & Tshistjakov, Y. A. <i>Papilio</i> (<i>Achillides</i>) <i>dehaanii</i> C. et R. Felder, 1864 (Lepidoptera, Papilionidae) from the continental part of the Russian Far East. <i>Euroasian Entomological Journal</i> 20(2): 82-85.
<i>Papilio enganius</i> was considered different from <i>Papilio helenus</i> , and distributed in Enggano, Borneo and Lombok.	Allio, R., Nabholz, B., Wanke, S., Chomicki, G., Pérez-Escobar, O. A., Cotton, A. M., Clamens, A-L., Kergoat, G. J., Sperling, F. A. H. & Condamine, F. L. (2021). Genome-wide macroevolutionary signatures of key innovations in butterflies colonizing new host plants. <i>Nature communications</i> , 12(1), 1-15.

<i>Papilio heringi</i> was considered different from <i>Papilio fuscus</i> , and endemic from Halmahera Island.	MOONEN, J. (1996). A new natural hybrid of <i>Papilio</i> Linnaeus from W. Irian and remarks on <i>Papilio heringi</i> Niepelt from Halmahera (Lepidoptera, Papilionidae). <i>Lepidoptera Science</i> , 47(3), 185-188.
<i>Papilio hermeli</i> was considered different from <i>Papilio chikae</i> , endemic from Mindoro Island	Hardy, P. B., & Lawrence, J. M. (2017). Field guide to butterflies of the Philippines (p. 488)
<i>Papilio hippocrates</i> was considered different from <i>Papilio machaon</i>	Remington, C. L. (1960). Wide experimental crosses between <i>Papilio xuthus</i> and other species. <i>J Lep Soc</i> , 13, 151-164.
<i>Papilio humbloti</i> was considered different from <i>Papilio dardanus</i> , endemic to Comoro Islands	Allio, R., Nabholz, B., Wanke, S., Chomicki, G., Pérez-Escobar, O. A., Cotton, A. M., Clamens, A-L., Kergoat, G. J., Sperling, F. A. H. & Condamine, F. L. (2021). Genome-wide macroevolutionary signatures of key innovations in butterflies colonizing new host plants. <i>Nature communications</i> , 12(1), 1-15.
<i>Papilio meriones</i> was considered a different species from <i>Papilio dardanus</i> , endemic to Madagascar	Allio, R., Nabholz, B., Wanke, S., Chomicki, G., Pérez-Escobar, O. A., Cotton, A. M., Clamens, A-L., Kergoat, G. J., Sperling, F. A. H. & Condamine, F. L. (2021). Genome-wide macroevolutionary signatures of key innovations in butterflies colonizing new host plants. <i>Nature communications</i> , 12(1), 1-15.
<i>Papilio oviedo</i> was considered as a separated species from <i>Papilio thoas</i> , endemic to Cuba	AGUILA, R. N., & CAÑAMERO, A. B. (2012). A list of Cuban Lepidoptera (Arthropoda: Insecta). <i>Zootaxa</i> , 3384(1), 1-59.
<i>Papilio pallas</i> was considered different from <i>P. astyalus</i> .	Allio, R., Nabholz, B., Wanke, S., Chomicki, G., Pérez-Escobar, O. A., Cotton, A. M., Clamens, A-L., Kergoat, G. J., Sperling, F. A. H. & Condamine, F. L. (2021). Genome-wide macroevolutionary signatures of key innovations in butterflies colonizing new host plants. <i>Nature communications</i> , 12(1), 1-15.
<i>Papilio polyctor</i> was considered as a separated species from <i>Papilio bianor</i>	Lixin, Z., Xiaobing, W., Chunsheng, W., & Banghe, Y. (2009). Phylogenetic evaluation of <i>Papilio bianor</i> and <i>P. polyctor</i> (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae). <i>Oriental Insects</i> , 43(1), 25-32.
<i>Papilio prexaspes</i> was considered different from <i>Papilio fuscus</i> .	COTTON, A. M., & RACHELI, T. (2006). Notes on some Papilionidae of Laos and Vietnam. <i>Fragmenta entomologica</i> , 38(1), 145-154.
<i>Parnassius augustus</i> was considered a different species from <i>Parnassius imperator</i>	Omoto, K., Katoh, T., Chichvarkhin, A., & Yagi, T. (2004). Molecular systematics and evolution of the "Apollo" butterflies of the genus <i>Parnassius</i> (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae) based on mitochondrial DNA sequence data. <i>Gene</i> , 326, 141-147.
<i>Parnassius jacobsoni</i> and <i>Parnassius cardinal</i> were considered separated species from <i>Parnassius staudingeri</i> .	Korb, S. K. (2020). An annotated checklist of the tribus Parnassiini sensu Korshunov of the Old World (Lepidoptera, Papilionidae). <i>Acta Biologica Sibirica</i> , 6, 59.
<i>Parnassius mercurius</i> was considered different <i>P. jacquemontii</i>	Korb, S. K. (2020). An annotated checklist of the tribus Parnassiini sensu Korshunov of the Old World (Lepidoptera, Papilionidae). <i>Acta Biologica Sibirica</i> , 6, 59.

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56 Appendix S2

57 Literature used for the biogeographical survey of all modern Papilionidae 58 species*

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60 * In those cases in which two or more references contained geographical information for a species,
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964 **Appendix S3**

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966 **Table S3.1** Observed and simulated BSI values for Papilionidae. p: probability of the proportion of
 967 observed species being higher (bold), lower (italics) or non-significantly different (plain) to simulated
 968 proportions in Papilionidae.

BSI	% Observed	Monte Carlo Analysis			
		Mean %	Std. dev.	Range	p
1	54.50	38.00	1.60	32.00-45.00	<0.001
2	31.50	41.00	2.10	33.00-49.00	<i><0.001</i>
3	9.95	17.00	1.40	11.00-24.00	<i><0.001</i>
4	2.53	3.50	0.72	1.30-7.00	0.086
5	0.68	0.40	0.27	0.00-1.50	0.186
6	0.34	0.03	0.07	0.00-0.57	0.009
7	0.34	0.00	0.01	0.00-0.20	<0.001
8	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00-0.00	<0.001
9	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00-0.00	1.000
10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00-0.00	1.000

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979 **Figure S3.1.** Frequency distribution of Biomic Specialization Index (BSI) in Papilionidae subfamilies:

980 Papilioninae and Parnassiinae. Colours indicate the biomic specialization degree: red = specialist

981 species; yellow = semi-generalist species; blue = extreme generalist species. Dots indicate the

982 expected values by chance. *** = $p < 0,001$; ** = $0,01 > p > 0,001$; * = $0,05 > p > 0,01$; n.s = not significant.

983 Symbols above or below the dots indicate whether results are significantly higher (above) or lower

984 (bellow) than expected by chance.

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1000 **Table S3.2** Observed and simulated BSI values for Papilionidae subfamilies: Papilioninae and
 1001 Parnassiinae. p: probability of observed species being higher (bold), lower (italic) or non-significantly
 1002 different (plain) to simulated proportions.
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Papilioninae						Parnassiinae				
BSI	% Observed	Monte Carlo Analysis				% Observed	Monte Carlo Analysis			
		Mean %	Std. dev.	Range	p		Mean %	Std. dev.	Range	p
1	51.00	36.00	1.60	28.00-42.00	<0.001	77.60	51.00	4.80	29.00-67.00	<0.001
2	33.90	44.00	2.20	37.00-54.00	<i><0.001</i>	15.80	35.00	5.90	16.00-62.00	<i><0.001</i>
3	11.00	17.00	1.40	11.00-23.00	<i><0.001</i>	2.63	12.00	3.50	0.00-29.00	<i>0.001</i>
4	2.652	2.70	0.66	0.63-5.40	0.702	2.63	2.00	1.70	0.00-12.00	0.550
5	0.78	0.22	0.20	0.00-1.50	0.014	0.00	0.19	0.55	0.00-5.10	0.888
6	0.19	0.01	0.04	0.00-0.43	0.004	1.32	0.01	0.12	0.00-1.80	0.006
7	0.39	0.00	0.01	0.00-0.21	<0.001	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00-0.00	1.000
8	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00-0.00	1.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00-0.00	1.000

9	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00- 0.00	1.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00- 0.00	1.000
10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00- 0.00	1.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00- 0.00	1.000

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1008 **Table S3.3.** Observed and simulated distribution of biome specialist (BSI=1) Papilionidae species

1009 across different biomes. p: probability of the proportion of observed species being higher (bold), lower

1010 (italics) or non-significantly different (plain) to simulated proportions in Papilionidae among biomes.

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Biome	Papilionidae			Monte Carlo Analysis			
	Sp	Sp (BSI=1)	%	Mean %	Std. dev	Range	p
E.R	331	143	43.20	24.70	1.90	16.30-32.30	<0.001
T.W	330	101	30.61	24.60	1.90	17.30-31.80	<0.001
Sa	38	0	0.00	11.70	5.20	0.00-34.20	<i><0.001</i>
T.D	7	1	14.29	11.10	12.00	0.00-71.40	0.217
S.W	23	8	34.78	11.20	6.50	0.00-39.10	<0.001
T.F	117	15	12.82	13.60	3.00	2.56-27.40	0.556
B.F	52	6	11.54	12.00	4.40	0.00-30.80	0.777
St	58	40	68.97	12.10	4.30	0.00-32.80	<0.001
Ta	23	6	26.09	11.30	6.60	0.00-43.50	0.013
Tu	9	3	33.33	11.00	10.00	0.00-66.70	0.010

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Figure S3.2. Observed and simulated distribution of biome specialist species (BSI=1) in Papilioninae

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and Parnassiinae species across different biomes. *** = $p < 0,001$; ** = $0,01 > p > 0,001$; * =

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$0,05 > p > 0,01$; n.s = not significant. Symbols above or below the dots indicate whether results are

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significantly higher (above) or lower (below) than expected by chance. Colors for biomes as in Table

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Biome	Papilioninae							Parnassiinae						
				Monte Carlo Analysis							Monte Carlo Analysis			
	Sp	Sp (BSI=1)	%	Mean %	Std. dev	Range	p	Sp	Sp (BSI=1)	%	Mean %	Std. dev	Range	p
E.R	331	143	43.20	23.00	1.80	16.90- 29.30	<0.001	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00- 0.00	1.000
T.W	325	98	30.15	22.30	1.80	16.00- 28.90	<0.001	4	2	50.00	19.10	20.00	0.00- 100.00	0.023
Sa	38	0	0.00	8.95	4.50	0.00- 28.90	<0.001	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00- 0.00	1.000
T.D	7	1	14.29	8.42	11.00	0.00- 71.40	0.125	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00- 0.00	1.000
S.W	13	2	15.38	8.39	7.70	0.00- 46.20	0.101	10	6	60.00	20.40	12.00	0.00- 70.00	<0.001

T.F	108	14	12.96	10.50	2.80	0.93- 22.20	0.172	9	1	11.11	20.00	13.00	0.00- 77.80	0.142
B.F	36	3	8.33	8.86	4.70	0.00- 36.10	0.666	16	3	18.75	22.70	9.80	0.00- 62.50	0.317
St	13	0	0.00	8.41	7.70	0.00- 46.20	<i><0.001</i>	45	40	88.89	43.80	5.60	22.20- 64.40	<0.001
Ta	11	2	18.18	8.48	8.20	0.00- 45.50	0.041	12	4	33.33	21.30	11.00	0.00- 66.70	0.044
Tu	2	0	0.00	7.93	19.00	0.00- 100.00	0.180	7	3	42.86	15.00	15.00	0.00- 85.70	0.027

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1030 **Table S3.4.** Observed and simulated distribution of biome specialist (BSI=1) Papilioninae and Parnassiinae species across different biomes. p: probability of
1031 the proportion of observed species being higher (bold), lower (italics) or non-significantly different (plain) to simulated proportions in Papilionidae subfamilies,
1032 Papilioninae and Parnassiinae, among biomes.

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1034 **Table S3.5.** DR (Jetz et al., 2012) diversification rate statistical values grouped by species's
 1035 Biomic Specialization Index for all Papilionidae species present in the phylogeny.
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BSI	DR Mean Value	DR Max Value	DR Min Value	DR Value Range	DR standard deviation
1	0.1560	0.6101	0.0189	0.5912	0.0908
2	0.1403	0.6101	0.0262	0.5839	0.1042
3	0.1324	0.3706	0.0259	0.3447	0.0821
4	0.1151	0.2674	0.0609	0.2065	0.0562
5	0.1340	0.2050	0.0502	0.1548	0.0709
6	0.0814	0.1126	0.0502	0.0624	0.0442
7	0.1323	0.1669	0.0977	0.0692	0.0346
8	0.1339	0.1339	0.1339	-	-

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 1038 **Table S3.6** Model outputs for Phylogenetic ANOVA analysis of the relationship between biomic
 1039 specialization (BSI) and diversification rate, calculated under DR methodology.

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DR					
	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p
Group	7	26.113	3.7304	4.1452	0.0002
Residual	191	171.887	0.8999		

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1047 **Table S3.7.** Summary of model support for null (CID), binary state speciation and extinction (BiSSE) and hidden state speciation and extinction (HiSSE) trait-
 1048 dependent models. The coding indicates biomes specialist species as “1” and biome generalists, both moderate and extreme, as “0”. Best-fit model is
 1049 highlighted in bold.
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Model	NP	logL	AICc	ΔAICc	lambda0A	lambda1A	lambda0B	lambda1B	mu0A	mu1A	mu0B	mu1B
CID model	5	-1.536.813	3083,781	40,025	0,1072		0,1070		<0,0001		<0,0001	
full BiSSE model	6	-1.529.103	3070,424	26,668	0,0570	0,1509	-	-	<0,0001	<0,0001	-	-
HiSSE model for state 0	10	-1514,16	3058,897	15,141	0,0591	0,1611	0,0480	-	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001	-
HiSSE model for state 1	10	-1511,59	3043,756	0	0,1867	0,0990	-	0,0941	<0,0001	<0,0001	0,0000	<0,0001
full HiSSE model	16	-1.509.274	3061,994	18,238	0,0274	0,0860	0,1768	0,1655	0,0822	<0,0001	<0,0001	<0,0001
Model	q0A1A	q0A0B	q1A0A	q1A1B	q0B1A	q0B1B	q0B0A	q1B1A	q1B0B			
CID model					2,5278							
full BiSSE model	0,0787	-	0,1184	-	-	-	-	-	-			
HiSSE model for state 0	100,0000	0,1555	36,7148	-	-	-	3,37E-02	-	-			
HiSSE model for state 1	3,1265	-	4,7124	0,0077	-	-	-	0,0509	-			
full HiSSE model	0,0683	0,0010	0,2264	0,0000	0,0000	3,7900	<0,0001	0,1657	2,9203			

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